

Decentralizing Web Search: the PeARS search engine

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1. Introduction

Recent publications have highlighted a number of growing concerns related to the relevance and trustworthiness of Web search systems, all exacerbated by the advent of LLM-based solutions (Shah and Bender, 2022; 2024). Such concerns include a) the presence of ungrounded and biased information in search results (Noble, 2018); b) the impossibility to tailor the ranking algorithm to suit the user; c) various economic issues ranging from the monopolization of systems (Hovenkamp, 2024) to their impact on the environment (Dodge et al, 2022).

Aside from academic critique, there is also a common belief that Web search engines require immense resources to operate, making it daunting for communities or small enterprises to build alternatives to the dominant players. The PeARS project (Herbelot, 2016; <https://pearsproject.org>) aims at changing the status quo by providing the building blocks of an open-source, decentralized search engine. To achieve this, it combines algorithms that run on entry-level hardware, using both traditional and modern machine learning techniques. Its low resource consumption ensures that anybody can take part in the network, regardless of financial means.

The aim of this short contribution is two-fold. It will first give a bird's eye view of the PeARS framework, concentrating on the ethical issues it seeks to address. We will see how the system can be trained and populated and how it can be tailored to specific communities, for instance for underrepresented groups or minority languages. We will also give a glimpse into cross-instance search and show how to search the entire PeARS network from a local instance. Building on the proposal of Shah and Bender (2022) for an alternative search vision, it will be argued that PeARS supports the goals of *transparency*, *information literacy* and the requirement for the search system to be *free of economic structures* that might encourage the monetization of the service.

The second part of the talk will discuss the technical decisions that must be made to adhere to the ethical principles we set for ourselves. We will briefly cover the indexing and search algorithms and the challenges brought by decentralization. We will highlight how our multilinguality-first approach leads to the adoption of vector representations based on subwords rather than words, following the trend in deep learning methods while remaining outside of any 'AI' paradigm. The requirements for energy-efficiency will also be discussed, focusing on their impact on the PeARS algorithms at search time. Finally, decentralization itself will be addressed and it will be shown that federating search puts additional pressure on the accuracy of the indexing and search algorithms, with large centralized search engines being able to afford 'sloppier' solutions.

We will conclude that the development of true alternatives to the current search monopolies requires both a change in the general public assumptions and new technical solutions.

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3. References

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